

SEAGUARD: An Interoperability Framework for Maritime Border Security involving Unmanned Platforms

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Abstract

The SEAGUARD concept addresses a multi-domain (air, sea, underwater) maritime surveillance approach, involving the deployment, management and coordination of heterogeneous platforms, sensors and information technologies. SEAGUARD's aim is to deliver a high level of situational awareness through a holistic surveillance system fitted to the needs and ambition of modern border management authorities. The operational context of large maritime areas and the nature of threats - increasingly dynamic, transnational and highly mobile - reflect the growing need to have multiple and different types of authorities involved in and coordinating response efforts so that, working together, their common goals are achieved, with superior efficiency and effectiveness. Attaining the SEAGUARD vision requires a high level of interoperability between the diverse and heterogeneous participating entities (organizations, units, people) and technological systems (unmanned platforms and smart devices) in a collective working in a civil-military, cross-organisation and cross-border environment. To enable this advanced synchronization, the SEAGUARD Interoperability Framework (S.IF) implements a set of Command and Control (C2) rules and protocols among participating entities, benefitting from NATO C2 Approaches as foundational references for its novel interoperability approach.

1 INTRODUCTION

Securing the maritime borders in the European Union is a fundamental mission that is now facing considerable challenges. Instability, conflict and war in neighbouring regions in northern Africa, Middle East and Ukraine cause large-scale migration flows into the EU. In addition, a promising prosperous economic context makes Europe a highly valued destination not only for migrants, but also for criminal organisations involved with drug trafficking, contraband and human trafficking. In parallel, the ongoing European support to Ukraine raises concerns about the potential emergence and occurrence of hybrid threats to Europe's maritime infrastructures. As a result, enhanced maritime border surveillance capabilities are required to deter, monitor and respond to those challenges and threats, whose cross-border nature demand Member-State's improved interoperability and cooperation, from the Mediterranean to the Nordic Countries.

The SEAGUARD project aims at improving border surveillance capabilities by developing an innovative and integrated approach for cross-border missions to fight primary and secondary threats. SEAGUARD enables deploying, managing and coordinating multi-domain (air, sea, underwater) unmanned platforms, sensors and information technologies that complement current EU capabilities with an innovative, integrated and interoperable approach to maritime cross-border surveillance on threats related to vessels.

This paper presents the SEAGUARD project, describing its proposed surveillance capabilities and particularly focusing its innovative interoperability approach. The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: chapter 2 provides the relevant background context, introducing EU pressing maritime security challenges in maritime security, and past relevant research and development activities in maritime security; chapter 3 introduces the

SEAGUARD project, describing a reference use case, followed by applicable operational levels and command and control (C2) approaches; Chapter 4 presents the SEAGUARD Interoperability Framework, including its high level architecture; Chapter 5 concludes the paper, also presenting next steps.

2 BACKGROUND AND MOTIVATION

Illegal activities across external land and maritime borders are a threat to the security of the European Union. In its annual report, the European Border and Coast Guard Agency (FRONTEX) outlines irregular migration, including the Mediterranean routes drug trafficking, contraband, and human trafficking as the main concerns for European security (FRONTEX, 2025).

More specifically, modern maritime challenges and threats related to:

Terrorism and Piracy: Piracy off the coast of Somalia continues to be a threat, and there are concerns about terrorism in the Arabian Peninsula, particularly in the Red Sea and Gulf of Aden areas bordering Yemen. Vessel operators are advised to follow recommended Best Management Practices and register with relevant authorities when operating in these areas.

Illegal Trafficking: The maritime industry faces threats from illegal trafficking of goods and people, as well as illegal fishing and pollution.

- Specifically concerning **drug trafficking**, the EU drug market is estimated at EUR 31 billion, being noted a trend towards trafficking larger individual consignments of drugs by sea, exploiting containers flowing through global logistics hubs (EUROPOL, 2024). Pertaining to cocaine alone, at least 282 tonnes destined for Europe were seized in 2020, approximately 171 tonnes in EU ports (EUDA, 2022). Criminal networks have been exploiting novel approaches, like the use of semi-submersibles to transport high quantities of drugs. Recently, in a joint operation involving Portuguese and Spanish authorities, a semi-submersible was intercepted transporting 6.5 tons of cocaine (PJ, 2025).

Migration flows within the Mediterranean are estimated to involve thousands of people travelling by boat from the northern coasts of Africa and Turkey. Only in 2024, there were almost 200 thousand irregular arrivals to Europe, being estimated 3,804 deaths or disappearances (IOM, 2025).

Cybersecurity: Maritime systems are more interconnected and supported by information and communications technologies (ICT) infrastructures, emphasizing the need for robust cybersecurity measures and maritime cybersecurity training to protect against

cyber threats.

Environmental Threats: The oceans face numerous environmental challenges, including:

- **Climate Change:** Rising sea levels, ocean acidification, and altered ocean chemistry threaten marine ecosystems and species.
- **Pollution:** Land-based activities contribute to over 80% of marine pollution, with air pollution responsible for almost one-third of toxic contaminants and nutrients entering coastal areas and oceans.
- **Overfishing:** The United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization estimates that 35.5% of fish stocks are either fished to capacity or overfished (Sharma *et al.*, 2025).

Piracy: This latest threat, mainly focused in the Red Sea, is related as the combination results of the above threats or new related with the use of guns/unmanned vehicles from non-flagged/registered as military vessels.

Finally, the European Commission has raised the importance for Member States to respond to **hybrid threats**, which include actions to influence and exploit vulnerabilities to incur damage below the threshold of overt aggression. These threats are a mixture of coercive and subversive activities, conventional and unconventional methods (DG-DEFIS, 2022), which have become increasingly common over the past fifteen years, and are expected to grow both in frequency and impact in the future (Jungwirth *et al.*, 2023). For example, several incidents were detected in submarine cables connecting several Member States, risking severe disruptions in essential functions and services across the EU (EC, 2025).

The vast challenges and wide threat landscape observed in the EU maritime space demands for advanced border surveillance capabilities to deter, monitor, detect and respond, while also supporting multi-agency and cross-border operations.

Regarding security at EU's external borders, FRONTEX has an important role to perform, in terms of assisting Member States secure the borders. The evolving border challenges led FRONTEX to engage in research and development and innovation activities to enhance border security technologies and methodologies. Specific technologies, such as robotics, artificial intelligence and the internet of things are fundamental drivers in the design and implementation of new border security capabilities. Multi-domain connectivity is critical in supporting surveillance and monitoring operations with the required level of command and control and

information sharing capabilities. These services require a reliable and secure communication infrastructure suitable for combined environments. In this context, naval manoeuvrability can be enhanced by improving maritime situational awareness capabilities, namely in the areas of surveillance awareness, maritime patrol and surveillance aircraft, long-range coastal networks, UAV-based tactical radar maritime surveillance and maritime C2 capabilities based on automatic data link systems and data fusion systems. Further, advanced naval manoeuvrability is directly influenced by long endurance at sea, which is reinforced through the deployment of autonomous robotic platforms and the existence of adaptable offshore patrol vessels.

The use of multi-domain unmanned systems can be a powerful differentiator in security missions carried out today. Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV) are already being deployed for border surveillance, as they are capable of providing real-time data over large distances, successfully detecting unauthorized activities and potential targets. Their relative small size and thus higher manoeuvrability and agility enable rapid deployment in response to emergencies without risking human lives. On the maritime domain, Unmanned Surface Vehicles (USV) are highly capable assets for patrolling coastal areas, and their greater endurance allows for better monitoring of sea traffic in case suspicious activities are detected. Suitably equipped USVs, carrying sensors for target detection and tracking as well as mechanisms for automatic life-rafts deployment, can also be key assets to be used in search and rescue (SAR) missions in maritime distress situations. Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (UUV) can fill a gap in the underwater domain, allowing surveillance activities to take place below sea surface. These platforms can remain covert while navigating in the underwater environment looking for threats, such as submarines being used for smuggling operations. UUVs also play an important role in underwater infrastructure inspection, protecting critical infrastructure such as ports and communication cables. Arguably, joint multi-domain operations that involve different types of autonomous systems, cooperating towards a common goal, have the potential to significantly improve current FRONTEX capabilities by empowering complete situational awareness in the operational environment.

Project	Timeline	Multi-domain System	Multi-sensor data fusion	Unified asset C2	Long-term operations
PERSEUS	2011-2015	YES	NO	NO	NO
ROBORDER (1)	2017-2021	YES	NO	YES	NO
CAMELOT (2)	2017-2021	YES	YES	YES	NO
COMPASS 2020 (3)	2019-2021	YES	NO	YES	NO
ARESIBO (4)	2019-2022	YES	NO	YES	NO
NESTOR	2021-2023	YES	NO	YES	NO
EURMARS (5)	2022-2025	NO	-	-	YES
FLEXICROSS	2022-2025	YES	YES	NO	-
I-SEAMORE (6)	2023-2025	NO	-	YES	NO

Table 1 - Analysis of EC Funded Projects in Border Surveillance

Notes: (1) The project addresses radar and visual-based detection separately. It addresses multi-domain, but the UUVs only perform environmental monitoring. (2) Due to COVID19, experiments were performed through simulation. (3) An AUV is deployed a priori and surveys the area around traffickers typical routes. (4) Multi-domain, but the UUVs was only used to scan the sea bottom to detect objects thrown out by smugglers. (5) Only aerial and ground surveillance. (6) Only aerial and water surface.

Specifically, the use of a multi-domain unmanned systems swarm allows the acquisition of multi-domain sensor data (such as radar, image and acoustics-based data) that can be fused and processed by intelligent AI-enabled algorithms to improve threat detection and classification capabilities. Such capabilities can only materialize with high-speed low latency communication system infrastructure, enabling real-time communication and coordination among the unmanned platforms in the swarm.

Over the last decade, the European Commission funded numerous civilian innovative projects in the field of border surveillance, as presented in Table 1. Based on public information available in the EC CORDIS portal¹, the following conclusions are presented:

- The concept of cooperative multi-robot missions, where robots work together towards achieving a common goal (e.g. threat detection), was not subject to study. The assets were typically deployed in isolation and restricted to follow a specific planned mission. Cooperation among robots has several advantages such as reducing threat tracking error, improving localization performance and improving communication performance by reconfiguring the position of the nodes (robots).
- Although there is a clear focus on designing a functional system that is able to perform multi-domain border surveillance, none of the projects addressed the subject of long-term operations, focusing on systems' long-term reliability, maintenance, and endurance nor on dynamic allocation of resources to face multithreats or hybrid threats. The maritime environment can be extremely

¹ Online: <https://cordis.europa.eu/>

harsh, and equipment usually requires specific regular maintenance for ensuring superior system operability.

- Based on the available information, a surprising gap was the absence of multi-sensor data fusion within the projects. Most systems perform threat detection and classification using single types of sensors, like radar and optical sensors, but only fusing this data with information of the same type (e.g. fusing information from different cameras, but not between camera and radar or camera and acoustic data). Specific operational constraints may have caused this absence, since the different types of data are available at different timeframes, but nonetheless it seems to be an important step towards improving situational awareness on the operational area.
- Cross-border operations, including procedures and mechanisms for enabling transnational information sharing and for coordinating joint actions, were not addressed as key themes in any funded project. The cross-border dimension is critical, since addressing security challenges that are transnational in nature, require neighboring Member States to actively cooperate and share information.

3 THE SEAGUARD PROJECT

SEAGUARD [SEAGUARD] is an Innovation Action that received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 101168489 (SEAGUARD, 2025). It involves 14 organisations across Europe, including universities, companies and border authorities.

The SEAGUARD concept fosters multi-domain (air, sea, underwater) maritime surveillance through the deployment, management and coordination of heterogeneous platforms, sensors and information technologies. Its aim is to deliver high-level situational awareness through holistic surveillance approaches to border management authorities, operating in a multi-agency cross-border contexts. It fills relevant gaps identified in previous research activities, with a high innovation potential in border surveillance.

SEAGUARD involves the design, development, testing, and deployment of a multi-domain AI-enabled cross-border surveillance system able to operate in cross-border missions, that will incorporate multiple sensing and communications technologies integrated in both fixed and mobile platforms to face multithreats reactively or

proactively. It will combine unmanned aerial, surface and underwater vehicles, SMART submarine cables, with advanced analytics and decision support. The system will be able to monitor and detect various types of threats, including illegal border crossings, smuggling of contraband, illegal fisheries and terrorist activities. The project will leverage new technologies and data analytics, enhanced by multi-domain autonomous cooperative platforms, to provide real-time information and advanced situational awareness to border authorities, enabling them to detect and respond to potential threats coming from the air, sea surface or underwater, more effectively. Data sharing will follow the operational needs of each C2 Center, filtered under possible restrictions due to bilateral agreements between countries. As the SEAGUARD system will integrate different technologies, sensors, unmanned vehicles of different OEMs under the same mission control, the system will provide an interoperability framework that enables the deployment of different federated systems with maximum interoperability.

3.1 A REFERENCE USE CASE

Figure 1 illustrates the SEAGUARD overall concept in action, based on a use case on irregular flow of people. Following an incident involving a boat used to transport irregular migrants, several individuals fall into the sea. The incident occurs close to the maritime border between two Member States. Each Member State has assets deployed in the area for surveillance and patrolling purposes.

Figure 1 - SEAGUARD Interoperability in a Cross-Border Maritime Scenario

Scenario Challenges

This scenario involves an incident occurring near the border between nations X and Y. UAVs from Nation Y are present performing routine surveillance, detecting the

incident. Information is reported via satellite communications to central headquarters. Given that the incident occurs in Nation Y waters and a ship from nation X is close to the incident, a joint coordinated effort is launched. Nation Y shares incident information with Nation X and allows the ship from Nation X to perform humanitarian assistance in Nation Y waters. Moreover, real-time aerial UAV video is sent to the Nation X ship, allowing its staff to understand the actual and current incident details and the progress over time. A ship from Nation Y (i.e., ship Y) is also requested to assist.

This scenario entails a number of challenges, involving both governance and technological aspects, faced by two nations with different organisational structures, definitions or understanding on threats, processes and personnel, employing different assets and technologies (e.g., C2 systems, data and network/communications). Notwithstanding, they need to jointly respond to a cross-border single incident at sea.

First and foremost, there needs to exist willingness for collaboration and protocols in-place between Nations. Then, effective response with minimal delay requires fast information exchange (ideally in digital form) between the Nation’s headquarters and the patrolling ship from Nation X (ship X). Finally, in order to achieve a higher level of awareness and understanding about the incident, the surveillance UAV needs to send real-time video to ship X, which requires advanced technological capabilities in interoperability (ship X and UAV having compatible radio technologies), data processing (video protocols) and communications (high throughput, low latency). Simultaneously, a common operational picture is generated between participating entities, with continuous information exchange in place (ship X, ship Y to nation X and nation Y headquarters).

3.2 SEAGUARD OPERATIONAL LEVELS

SEAGUARD will contribute to the establishment of cross-border cooperation mechanisms and procedures enabled by the efficient exchange of information/intelligence and resources, while ensuring that the sovereignty of each nation is preserved. Data sharing is needed and follows the operational needs of each Command and Control (C2) system filtered under possible restriction due to bilateral agreements between countries.

SEAGUARD aims an alignment with existing organizational practices, identifying three main operational levels, each exhibiting specific characteristics, as presented next:

- The strategic level encompasses organizations and authorities, being a multi-domain, cross-border, multi-organization level. Deals with the management of high-impact incidents and/or multiple incidents. It involves following formal intra- and extra-procedures between authorities for interoperability. At this level, C2 systems need to provide an effective overview of incidents/events that could be in high number. This level does not require near real-time performance.
- The tactical level encompasses units belonging to specific domains and specializations, managing several platforms (e.g., ships). Most procedures and processes are internal to the unit or organization. It may have C2 systems responsible for platform coordination, as well as constituent systems/subsystems. It deals with management of single incidents and multiple missions/tasks. This level requires near real-time performance.
- The platform level encompasses platforms (e.g., single ship) and deployed assets/staff, including unmanned vehicles (UxVs). Procedures and processes are internal to the unit or organization. C2 systems perform local coordination, i.e., single platform and its constituent systems/subsystems. It deals with the execution of assigned missions/tasks. This level requires real-time performance.

The three operational levels and their characteristics are presented in Table 2.

Table 2 - SEAGUARD Operational Levels

Operational Level	Main Characteristics
Strategic level	Multi-domain; Multi-organizations; Cross-border; Multi-incidents; Multi-threats; Non real-time
Tactical level	Multiple units; Single incident; Multi to single mission; Single or multiple threats; Near real-time
Platform level	Single unit/platform/device; Single mission; Single threat; Near to real-time

In order to work together, organizations and authorities need to put in place capabilities allowing coordination, exchange of information (subject to filtering) and sharing of resources – to the extent that has been accepted, agreed and supported – between participating entities.

As an example using the three operational layers frame, organizations may accept interacting at strategic level

only, limiting interoperability to non real-time information and high-level decisions. Alternatively, when accepting interactions at platform level, involved entities (e.g., platforms, UxVs) share missions and tasks, deciding on the best course of action, with the exchange of information occurring in real-time directly with each other. Inherent in these examples is the need to have certain capabilities so that a desired level of interoperability can be achieved: at strategic level, critical information is shared between organizations with access to highly capable infrastructures (e.g., broadband networks); at platform level, highly mobile systems need to deal with a fast pace of change and synchronize actions, thus a high level of integration is required (communications protocols, data formats and workflows).

3.3 REFERENCING AND INSTANTIATING C2 APPROACHES

Given that organizations are required to define the rules and extent in which interoperability should occur, different conceptual interoperability models need to be considered, addressing governance-related aspects.

SAFEGUARD refers to the work conducted by the NATO group SAS-065 (SAS-065, 2010) that developed the NATO Network Enabled Capability C2 Maturity Model (N2C2M2), a maturity model defining different C2 approaches pertaining to a collection of *entities*², characterized by the following characteristics:

- *Allocation of Decision Rights*: actual rights exercised by the entities in a mission, including capability to dynamically reallocate.
- *Patterns of Interaction*: actual occurrence of interactions and collaborations, including the ability to have face-to-face or virtual meetings, the connectivity of the infostructure, and the degree of interoperability that exists between and among a set of participants (technical, semantic, and cooperability).
- *Distribution of Information*: extent to which the information needed to accomplish required tasks is available to each participant.

The above characteristics are used to define five classes of C2 approaches as presented in Figure 2.

C2 Approach	Allocation of Decision Rights to the Collective	Patterns of Interaction Among Participating Entities	Distribution of Information (Entity Information Positions)
Edge C2	Not Explicit, Self-Allocated (Emergent, Tailored, and Dynamic)	Unlimited As Required	All Available and Relevant Information Accessible
Collaborative C2	Collaborative Process and Shared Plan	Significant Broad	Additional Information Across Collaborative Areas/Functions
Coordinated C2	Coordination Process and Linked Plans	Limited and Focused	Additional Information About Coordinated Areas/Functions
De-Conflicted C2	Establish Constraints	Very Limited Sharply Focused	Additional Information About Constraints and Seams
Conflicted C2	None	None	Organic Information

Figure 2 - The N2C2M2 C2 Approaches. Source: (SAS-065, 2010)

SAFEGUARD takes inspiration on the SAS-065 C2 approaches, using them as a conceptual reference for analysing the C2 structure, information flows and extent of interactions, across the three operational layers. It is noted that the SEAGUARD scope is mainly technological, although still considering procedures and practices in place by authorities.

Figure 3 illustrates two nations (A and B) operating in their own area of responsibility (AoR) employing a C2 structure across the three operational levels. At this stage, both nations operate independently.

Figure 3 - Nations A and B employing an independent C2 structure across the three operation levels

In this exemplary use case, the incident involves irregular flow of people, with victims at sea. The incident occurs near the maritime border between two nations. Nation A assigns resources to perform rescue operations, while Nation B has nearby resources providing additional assistance.

² Entity refers to an actively participating organization, unit, authority or group, and can also include an individual. In the context of

autonomous systems, one can conceptually also consider a UAV or AI-agent (SAS-065, 2010).

Figure 4 – Instantiating C2 approaches in SEAGUARD.
 Left: De-conflicted C2. Middle: Coordinated C2. Right: Collaborative C2

Next, three C2 approaches are instantiated and described in the context of this use case, allowing to depict the level of cooperation and interaction that can be expected. Conflicted C2 is excluded since it reflects a case where there is no interoperability, thus an undesired state in SEAGUARD. Also Edge C2 is excluded since it reflects a fully decentralised approach, currently reflecting an unfeasible state by current practices.

De-conflicted C2

Depicted in Figure 4 (left), De-conflicted C2 approach aims to avoid adverse cross-impacts between participating entities. There is a partition of space, time or both, following bilateral agreements. Organizational boundaries are well defined and strict. Decision-making is well defined and follows established rules (hierarchical based). Information exchange occurs at the minimal required level (need-to-know basis) and flows vertically within the formal organization. Cross-organization exchange occurs at strategic level to avoid conflicting actions and violation of agreed constraints. In this example, given there is no interoperability at tactical and platform levels, it is decided at strategic level to allow Nation A assets to enter Nation B's space to rescue victims.

Coordinated C2

Depicted in Figure 4 (middle), Coordinated C2 aims to develop relationships and linkages between participating entities to increase overall effectiveness. It requires plans and actions to be coordinated, by sharing the operating space according to plan. Interactions mostly follow the formal structure (vertical and hierarchical), while some horizontal exchanges might occur to ensure coordination of actions at lower levels. Organizational boundaries at lower levels become less strict as a result of a multi-entity coordinated response. Interoperability needs to exist to achieve a common intent and obtain a sustained degree

of information sharing and interactions to maintain coordinated actions). Cross-organisation exchange occurs mostly at strategic level, but requires exchanges at tactical level to ensure coordinated actions. In this example, a joint plan is developed between Nation A and Nation B allowing a coordinated rescue operation involving resources from both nations. This allows increasing response capacity.

Collaborative C2

Depicted in Figure 4 (right), Collaborative C2 aims to achieve significant synergies by negotiating and establishing a **single shared plan** at collective level, considering the combined use of all capabilities. The operating space is shared. Organizational boundaries are less strict, as participating entities work together and share resources.

The single shared plan can be adjusted dynamically and needs to be propagated across all assets, requiring force synchronization. There is the need for extensive information exchange, both vertically and horizontally (across all levels). This requires a high level of integration and interoperability at various domains across several platforms. A particular element in this approach is the possibility to dynamically share resources and capabilities from one nation to another: depicted by the blue arrow, a patrolling entity from Nation A requests and gains control over a UAV from Nation B. This approach requires high levels of trust and accepting delegating/relieving decision rights.

4 THE SEAGUARD INTEROPERABILITY FRAMEWORK

This section describes the SEAGUARD Interoperability Framework (S.IF), the structure that implements a set of rules and protocols for Command and Control (C2) in SEAGUARD, following applicable agreements among the participating entities.

From a technological perspective, interoperability achieved a strong momentum in the digital transformation era, in which ICT started connecting computer systems to exchange information and perform coordinated tasks. In the security and military domains, the digital transformation gave rise to the concept of Network Enabled Capability (NEC), promptly adopted by NATO (NNEC), whose purpose consisted in exploiting network systems and ICT to achieve competitive advantage in military/conflict operations. As stated by NATO, “NNEC is about people first, then processes, and finally technology.” (NATO, 2015)

As introduced in section 3, SEAGUARD’s operational context (large maritime areas) and the nature of possible threats (e.g., dynamic, transnational and highly mobile) mean that multiple and different types of authorities will need to be involved and, by working together towards achieving a common goal or objective, can be more effective and efficient. In SEAGUARD, interoperability is understood as the ability for different entities to work together to achieve a common goal or objective, responding reactively or proactively on dynamic multi-threats. It applies both to human and technological systems and may involve processes, data and communication protocols. When working together in a particular mission, entities exhibit appropriate interoperability levels, in order to achieve the required coordination and synchronization of effects, while avoiding duplication of effort and even preventing adverse cross-impacts and/or conflicting effects. As in most recent detected hybrid threat incidents it is quite usual secondary threats to involve as primary, the quick adaptation of tactics, missions or resources to face them becomes a crucial security or safety factor.

S.IF delivers a common frame allowing components (e.g., services, applications and systems) operated by different entities (e.g., border authorities, rescue organisations) to join the **SEAGUARD federation** (i.e., a common shared digital space for exchange of information and collaboration) to offer capabilities (herein represented as services) and access existing services. The S.IF concept allows to build a set of joint capabilities by integrating services and data provided by coalition entities. It is noted that the federated nature of SEAGUARD preserves ownership and control of services to the providing entity. By establishing well defined boundaries and not limiting the extent of collaboration, S.IF ranges from delivering simple data exchange interoperability between different systems, up to multiplying the overall capability set by combining services and functions brought by the different components and assets present in the SEAGUARD federation.

Being a technological artifact, an entity needs to provide a S.IF connector that follows the S.IF rules and protocols, in order to join a SEAGUARD federation.

- A component connecting to S.IF is called a **S.IF node**.

In addition, the SEAGUARD federation requires the existence of core management and administration functions over threat analysis and missions preparations reactively or proactively.

- In each SEAGUARD federation, a **S.IF manager node** is responsible for managing the federation, including functions like authentication, registration, discovery and access to resources.

Following the S.IF, each member of a force coalition is a S.IF node that can integrate its applications and data into the federation, either by being directly compliant with S.IF, or by interfacing via a connector (i.e., **S.IF connector**). In addition, where direct integration is not feasible, a **S.IF gateway** can be used as an intermediate node between the component and the S.IF.

Following the approach developed in (Manso *et al.*, 2023), the S.IF concept is illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5 - The SEAGUARD Federation: S.IF nodes can be applications, services and platforms. Nodes can have native support or require a S.IF connector. Federated nodes form the SEAGUARD interoperability space.

S.IF allows components (e.g., applications and UAVs) to join the SEAGUARD federation, by complying with a set of principles, business processes, and technologies. Components can comprise C2 systems, software applications, unmanned platforms (e.g., UAV, USV, UUV) and smart devices. External systems and data sources – like weather information, CISE, AIS information – can also be integrated by developing compatible S.IF connectors, as illustrated in Figure 6.

Figure 6 - S.IF Main Capabilities in the S.IF Interoperability Space

4.1 HIGH LEVEL ARCHITECTURE

S.IF enables heterogeneous platforms and components to connect and interact with each other to achieve a common goal. In order to achieve the necessary effect, S.IF comprises the following main capabilities:

- **S.IF general functionalities**, consisting of network-enabled functions and rules to build the interoperability space.
- **C2 system**, consisting of a system with the ability to monitor and allocate resources according to pre-defined rules (unit, organisation or federation specific).
- **AI system**, consisting of innovative functions based on Artificial Intelligence used for improving threat analysis, mission awareness and decision support.
- **Unmanned platforms and smart devices**, consisting of (i) multi-domain vehicles (air, surface, underwater) carrying mission-specific payload (e.g., EO, thermal, SAR); and (ii) connected devices incorporating intelligent features.
- **Communications**, consisting of the ability to exchange data in S.IF, following defined rules, protocols and data models. It includes APIs and gateway components.

The high level architecture of S.IF is depicted in Figure 7 and its main elements are described next.

S.IF follows a service-oriented architecture, interacting through well defined APIs to obtain a highly modular and scalable system. The S.IF logical architecture is grouped into the components described next.

4.1.1 S.IF General (PARTICLE)

The S.IF general provides foundational network-enabled functions and rules allowing managing and orchestrating federation resources.

Core Services provide functions required to manage and operate the SEAGUARD federation. They provide login functions, registration and discovery of resources within the federation. Within a federation, these services are provided by the S.IF Manager.

Communications services provide communications capabilities to allow information exchange within the SEAGUARD federation. Due to the heterogeneous nature of entities, different technologies are foreseen, ranging from acoustics to radio/RF.

Information Services deal with the ability to store and access data in different forms. SEAGUARD services include storage systems (databases, filesystem, multimedia), logging, message broker and access to RESTful API services.

Operational Services deliver the SEAGUARD functions necessary to conduct a mission or activity, aimed for end-users. They refer to specific capabilities like surveillance, management of incidents, tasks and victims.

Figure 7 - S.IF High Level Architecture

Security and Information Assurance addresses security related aspects, including controlling access to the SEAGUARD federation (via authentication and authorization), information integrity and audi

External interfaces relate to the exchange of information in SEAGUARD to/from external systems, like CISE, FRONTEX, satellite dark fleet monitoring, weather forecast systems or 3rd party systems in general.

4.1.2 Node Capabilities and Data Collection

Data collection operates through S.IF External Interfaces and Gateway Components, managing diverse source types including the IoT/Sensors Layer encompassing distributed sensor networks and drones (UAVs) providing aerial surveillance capabilities, fixed cameras, surface vehicles (USVs) contributing to maritime patrol data, underwater vehicles (UUVs) supplying subsurface monitoring, fixed sensors offering persistent surveillance coverage, environmental data sources providing meteorological and oceanographic measurements, and external systems contributing intelligence feeds and coordination data.

4.1.3 AI System (data)

The SEAGUARD AI System operates within the Processing and Storage Layer, integrating with S.IF services to provide maritime surveillance and decision support. The system interacts with S.IF to discover assets, receive data events, perform analysis, generate tactical objects, and create alerts. Its main components are described next.

The SEAGUARD **Data lake** is a central repository and processing hub for information flowing through the maritime surveillance network, designed to handle diverse data types at varying scales and velocities (see data collection above), while maintaining integration with S.IF services. It includes a data ingestion layer that handles high-throughput data intake rates generated throughout the SEAGUARD system. It is optimized for handling the diverse data types and rates generated by the various sensors and platforms in the SEAGUARD system, ensuring that no data is lost even during peak operational periods. It includes the following subcomponents:

- **Ingestion Layer:** Handles high-throughput intake through queuing systems designed to accommodate diverse data types and rates generated throughout the SEAGUARD network. Stream processing performs real-time transformation while batch processing handles scheduled historical analysis, ensuring no data loss during peak operational periods.
- **Processing Layer:** Provides feature extraction for ML

algorithms, data summarization, and query optimization. Maintains low latency for critical alerts, near real-time processing for operational awareness, and efficient response times for complex analytical queries.

- **Storage Components:** Three-tier architecture with processed data storage for immediate use, curated storage for analytics, and archived storage for compliance. Includes data retention policies maintaining critical data for investigation periods and operational data with long-term archival.

It is important to note that the responsible preparation of AI systems to accomplish this role is based on quality data obtained from federated trusted sources only.

4.1.4 AI System (DSS and maritime services)

The AI DSS Engine provides AI-driven capabilities for maritime surveillance and security, leveraging artificial intelligence techniques to enhance detection, classification, and threat assessment.

- **Data aggregation** combines multi-source data creating comprehensive operational pictures through spatial, temporal, entity, and statistical aggregation across geographic areas and time scales from tactical to strategic planning horizons.
- **Data classification and filtering** organizes data using intelligent algorithms. Vessel classification operates by type, size, and behavior using machine learning trained on maritime databases. Event classification categorizes by severity and operational relevance, while anomaly classification identifies deviations from expected patterns with dynamic filtering adapting to mission requirements.
- **Data curation and clustering** employs advanced processing techniques including semantic enrichment from external databases, entity resolution linking related data across sources, and relationship mapping establishing connections between entities and events for higher-level maritime situation understanding.
- **Object Detection & Classification** identifies objects using computer vision and machine learning. Detects vessels, persons, debris, marine life, and maritime infrastructure with high resolution, high fps processing, and very low noise ratios. Processes aerial imagery, sensor data, thermal infrared and radar data.
- **Vessel Behavior Analysis** examines movement patterns using behavioral analytics and machine learning. Route analysis detects shipping lane deviations, speed assessment evaluates unusual maneuvers, considering contextual factors including weather, traffic density, and regional security concerns.

- **Threat assessment** evaluates security risks through sophisticated algorithms incorporating vessel characteristics, behavioral patterns, location, and intelligence information. Generates risk scores with confidence levels and predictive assessment for proactive threat identification.
- **Anomaly detection** identifies unusual patterns using statistical methods and machine learning including z-score analysis, isolation forests, and contextual evaluation considering environmental conditions and traffic patterns.

4.1.5 C2 System Component

Within SEAGUARD, the C2 system constitutes a cornerstone of the mission architecture, ensuring robust coordination, supervision, and dynamic management of unmanned platforms and associated operational assets. It enables real-time and strategic-level decision-making by facilitating seamless interactions between human operators, autonomous units, and external systems.

A key feature of the C2 component is its support for multiple command approaches — deconflicted, coordinated, and collaborative — aligned with the NATO Network Enabled Capability (NEC) Command and Control Maturity Model (SAS-065, 2010). This flexibility allows stakeholders to select the most appropriate control schema based on operational requirements and mission criticality.

The system offers full interoperability and modular scalability, supporting integration with diverse Ground Control Stations (GCS), third-party applications, and legacy infrastructures via secure APIs and gateway-based communication protocols. Its capabilities include **dynamic mission planning, route definition, role distribution, and real-time re-tasking**, all governed by strict role-based access controls and cybersecurity protocols.

Visualisation Services play an essential role within the SEAGUARD C2 ecosystem. These services provide functions to generate situational awareness and understanding of on-going operations, such as building a **Common Operational Picture (COP)**, generating **real-time dashboards**, and offering **statistical overviews**. This visualization layer ensures that all stakeholders, regardless of their role, can interpret the operational environment effectively and make informed decisions.

Moreover, the C2 system incorporates advanced features such as sensor data fusion, AI-assisted planning, alert handling, diagnostics, network monitoring, and audit trail generation. It balances autonomous decision-making with manual override options, empowering operators to retain

control in critical scenarios.

In essence, the SEAGUARD C2 component not only orchestrates operational workflows and data exchanges but also acts as the intelligence core of the system, driving coordinated, secure, and efficient maritime mission execution, in a multi-agency cross-border context.

4.1.6 Communications

Communications deal with physical information exchange, supporting exchange data in S.IF. It is a conceptual component that can be realised in different ways, including through network adapters, gateways and dedicated hardware solutions. A common layer is required following an all-over-IP approach facilitating interoperability and long-term support in SEAGUARD.

Concerning communications technologies, it is considered state-of-the-art and emerging wired and wireless technologies: cellular networks (4G, 5G and 6G), IEEE 802.11 (i.e., Wi-Fi), optical fiber, satellite communications and dedicated broadband radio, including software defined radio (SDR) and cognitive radio (CR).

Multiple technologies need to be considered due to the heterogeneity of involved static and mobile multidomain assets. Connectivity will need to integrate different topologies as well, including star, ad-hoc/mesh and point-to-point. Furthermore, associated performance requirements will need to be analysed - including throughput, latency, energy-power and range - since they might enable/constrain the application of some services in SEAGUARD. For example, a low-throughput network will not support streaming real-time video required by AI-services.

4.2 NON-FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

S.IF considers aspects related with design and implementation with the aim to deliver a scalable, robust, reliable and secure architecture that is also compliant with legal framework and sound ethical guidelines.

S.IF design observes the following properties.

- **High availability**, as it provides critical services and supports 24/7/365 operational services in the security domain. **Target Value:** Above 99%.
- **High throughput with low latency**, able to sustain intensive workload and demand. **Target Value:** Response time and latency below the second (average time).
- **Resilience**, in the ability to recover from malfunctions and damage. Cluster and redundant deployments avoid single points-of-failure and allow to redirect

requests in case of local failure.

- **Support of reactive or proactive missions against threats**
- **Support for deployments of different size**, ranging from small to large scale. Component orchestration for multiple component deployment (on-demand) with load distribution allows adjusting to a varying number of requests. Support to distributed components allows horizontal growth.
- **Modular design** follows a loosely-coupled services-oriented architectural approach, having well defined functions and interfaces.
- **Support of remote updates** from secure servers, ensuring the system remains up-to-date.
- **Security by design**: SEAGUARD and its resources are restricted to authorized nodes only. The S.IF Manager Node provides the authentication mechanisms in the federation. To protect data confidentiality, communications are end-to-end encrypted, using strong encryption (digital certificates over TLS1.3), unless such is not feasible (e.g., constrained nodes like UUVs). All access and exchange of information is traceable and auditable.
- **Compliance with Privacy and Regulations**, with S.IF respecting legal compliance to international, European, and national laws. These include the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UN, 1982), the EU Artificial Intelligence Act (the “AI Act”) (EP, 2025), the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (EU, 2016) and the EU Human Trafficking and Maritime Security Regulations, including Montego Bay Treaty (UN, 1982, Articles 100–107). National legal frameworks from SEAGUARD participating member states (Greece, Portugal and Romania) are also observed.

5 CONCLUSION AND NEXT STEPS

Securing the maritime borders in the European Union is a fundamental mission that is now facing considerable challenges, given the presence of instability, conflicts and war in its neighbouring regions. As outlined by FRONTEX, major risks include security large-scale irregular migration (including infiltration of terrorists), drug trafficking, contraband and human trafficking. Responding to these challenges and risks requires advanced border surveillance capabilities to deter, monitor, detect and respond, while also supporting multi-agency and cross-border operations. As a result, the SEAGUARD project received support of the European Union’s Horizon Europe, aiming to improve border surveillance capabilities by integrating multi-domain (air, sea, underwater) unmanned platforms, sensors and information

technologies complementing current EU capabilities.

The collaborative cross-border multi-agency nature of SEAGUARD required an interoperable approach, resulting in the SEAGUARD Interoperability Framework (S.IF). Following a conceptual framework defined in NATO SAS-065, S.IF was created to deliver a common frame allowing to build a set of joint capabilities by integrating services and data provided by coalition entities. S.IF follows a federated approach preserving ownership and control of services to the providing entity.

S.IF capabilities include network-enabled functions and rules for interoperability, C2 system functions, AI system components, unmanned platforms, smart devices and communications. The framework is designed with modularity and scalability in mind, allowing the incorporation of future capabilities. Moreover, it is designed considering applicable ethical and legal frameworks.

As the SEAGUARD project unfolds, S.IF will be developed and demonstrated in realistic environmental conditions, using UxVs and technologies developed by partners with the capability to interoperate in order to achieve a common goal.

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See info at: <https://theseaguardproject.eu/>

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